

RELIGIOUS REPRESSION IN COMMUNISM. EXPRESSIONS OF THE DECOLONIZATION OF SOVIET MEMORY (THE CASE OF GHERASIM PĂDURARU) ¹

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ABSTRACT: Religious Repression in Communism. Expressions of the Decolonization of Soviet Memory (the Case of Gherasim Păduraru).

This paper proposes a reflection on religious repression under communism, illustrated by the case of priest Gherasim Păduraru. The terrifying biography of this priest – relentlessly pursued by the Securitate, slandered, poisoned with drugs including by his wife, who had signed the pact with the Securitate – represents the content of a volume of memoirs, entitled *Unmasking. The Secret of the Locked Gates*. The priest's recollections, the documents that accompany his testimonies constitute forms of decolonization of historical memory and represent proof of moral resistance and human dignity. The volume demonstrates that freedom of conscience is the "target" of totalitarian regimes. The communist system made the project of deindividualization and dehumanization of the human being a state program and only a strong will, a firm trust in moral principles and an ideologically unaltered religious conscience could constitute the barriers against the annihilation of the human being.

Keywords: *religious repression, communism, Securitate, religious conscience, priest, testimony, document.*

The communist period in the Romanian space meant vigilant control of all state institutions, but also of human private life². Numerous specialized studies, as well as fictions and artistic literature, have been written about

1 Article produced within the bilateral project „Decolonizing Memory: the Role of Cultural Expressions in Processing the Soviet Legacy in the Republic of Moldova and Romania” (PN-IV-P8-8.3-ROMD2023-0178).

2 Ioan-Gheorghe Rotaru, *Om-Demnitare-Libertate*, Cluj-Napoca, Editura Risoprint, 2019, pp. 214-215.

this period – with all that it meant, reprisals, organized famine, deportations, fierce censorship. In recent years, there has been a proliferation of memoirs, diaries, and autofictions, which reproduce a “narrative about oneself”³ from the victim’s point of view. For example, *The Book of Famine*, by Larisa Turea, has reached several circulations, become a cinematic product, a history lesson included in the curriculum in the Republic of Moldova, and has been awarded several important awards, including the National Award of the Republic of Moldova for 2022. The atrocities of the past must be disclosed and sanctioned so that they no longer return to the present, so that they no longer threaten the future – these works seem to say.

One such book of confession of history *as a lesson and as a warning* is the one signed by Gherasim Păduraru, *Demascarea. Taina porților zăvorâte*, which appears 40 years after it was written and over 30 years after the author’s death. The book is edited by his son, journalist Pavel Păduraru. The temporal distance that separates the actor’s self from the narrator’s self ensures the blending of several types of discourse: evocative, confessional and reflective on what has been experienced.

The stakes of the memorial discourse are ethical – to know the truth, „to somehow get out of the pit, to regain my honor”⁴, to thus break the transgenerational curse.

„It should be known that „tyranny, apart from the usual repressive methods - forced labor camps, prisons and insane asylums - also uses other, much more demonic methods, which do not aim at punishing the victims, but at their annihilation or, better said, the extermination of the human being”⁵

The author feels the urge to bear witness to a nebulous time, of terror and dehumanization of the human being. *Unmasking...* encompasses Păduraru’s existence starting from the interwar period, from 1922, the year of the writer’s birth, until 1978, when he wrote his memoirs. The author, Gherasim Păduraru, also a character in the book, experienced deportation, violence, and repression by the security forces for religious reasons. He is an Orthodox priest with great credibility among

3 Constantin Ticu, *Memoria autobiografică: definirea sau redefinirea propriei vieți*, Iași, Institutul European, 2004, p.269.

4 Gherasim Păduraru, *Demascarea sau Taina porților zăvorâte. Memorialistică*. Chișinău, Editura Prut internațional, 2023, p.312.

5 Ibid.

his parishioners. His refusal to collaborate with the Securitate made him dangerous. But even more dangerous was his credibility among his parishioners. The priest was called „golden-mouthed”, „undiscovered prophet”. His sermons gather people from all over the world, a group of supporters, „disciples”, who follow the advice and recommendations of their teacher is consolidated around him.

For the Securitate, this prestige of the priest’s image is increasingly threatening. The Securitate perceive the priest’s credibility as an attack on the authority of the state: „they could not see these people, who were fleeing from Christ, how this world weeps during prayer, how no one moves during the sermon because of the attention with which they listen to it. The atheists could not hear, during the service, the cries of the crowd: „undiscovered prophet”, nor listen to sermons that proved that Christ is truly the Son of God”⁶

The vigilance over the priest’s life is doubled by actions of defamation, public humiliation, and his illness through drugs and toxic medications. A fighter on the Romanian Army front, sent to Soviet camps, persecuted, slandered, soaked in narcotics, the priest was on the verge of madness and suicide. He is declared an „enemy”, „dangerous element”, „drug addict”, etc. - a stigma inherited from father to son. Gherasim Păduraru endures continuous persecution, is subjected to a long series of procedures of intimidation, psychological pressure, drug poisoning, the repressive mechanisms being executed including through his wife, Micuța, who had been forced to sign the pact with the Securitate. The stakes of these repressions, carried out without stopping for years on the priest, aim to convert the victim’s identity, to alter the values in which he believes.

The testimonies reconstruct – through the fidelity of personal and family memory and through documents taken from the Securitate archive – the experience of the authors’ families and other Bessarabians exiled, deported, tortured, subjected to psychological and physical extermination.

Identity vs. otherness

The identity of the authors of memoirs, diaries, and docu-fictions is built from their own perception of the past, from the resources of the imaginary

6 Gherasim Păduraru, *Demascarea sau Taina porților zăvorâte. Memorialistică*. Chișinău, Editura Prut internațional, 2023, p.163.

applied to that past, and from the perception of otherness (security documents, denunciations, testimonies of executioners, etc.).

Multiple identities are specific to victims of totalitarian systems. For those who did not betray their beliefs, resistance consisted of *dissociated identity*⁷. Family identity is different from social identity, forced to conform to Soviet norms. This multiplicity of identities is not a particularity of Soviet/communist society. Instead, the fact that these identities are tense and mutually cancel each other out is due to the oppressive context, the effort of “revolutionary” re-education, in fact demagogic, on the part of the Soviet state apparatus, and the real danger to which those who do not conform to official demagogy are exposed. For them, the problem arises of a programmed false identity, deliberately constructed by informants of the political police and imposed with the help of state law enforcement agencies, which usurps and tends to cancel the one assumed by the individual. This is how it happens that memorialists are assigned the status of “enemies of the people” or that they are seen as “enemy offspring”. As a rule, the writings of the victims reveal from the perspective of alterity a false identity of “enemy of the people”, or a dehumanized identity. Just as in Alexei Marinat’s *Concentration Diaries*, *Eu și lumea* or in the memoir *O projenitură dușmană*, by Nicolae Negru, identity is substituted by a number.

The ethics of memory

Authors of totalitarian memoirs always have an ethical stake in freeing the truth from beneath the layers of lies and political manipulation. The author of *Demascări* writes that he wants to recover his good name, denounce the criminals and present his own truth: “I was buried by atheists in the dust of the earth. That is, they killed my honor and today I stand like this, covered in garbage. I need to somehow get out of the hole, to regain my honor, but how can I do it other than to make people know the truth about me?”⁸. Identity in diaries, memoirs can be narrative and reflexive⁹.

7 Inga Sorocean, „Identitate și alteritate în imaginarul diaristic din Basarabia”, In: *Literatura și societatea în tranziție*. Coord. Ion Plămădeală, Chișinău, Editura Unu, 2023, p. 229.

8 Gherasim Păduraru, *Demascarea sau Taina porților zăvorâte. Memorialistică*, Chișinău, Editura Prut internațional, 2023, p.312.

9 Claude Dubar, *Criza identităților. Interpretarea unei mutații*, Chișinău, Știința, 2023, p. 294.

In Păduraru, the narrative is always accompanied by reflexivity, by a sententious reflexivity, since the recipient is children. The formulas are addressative, explanatory, the discourse is performative. For added credibility, the author's story is proven by facsimile of letters, of denunciatory acts extracted from the files of the Securitate. The documents open the floodgates of a time of horror, of propaganda manipulation, of the destruction of the human being. Denouncing these mechanisms of dehumanization is for the author Gherasim Păduraru a moral duty to restore personal dignity, to situate his biography on the coordinates of truth.

The daily newspaper under KGB repression

The book *Unmasking* is the narrative of a slippery, versatile daily life, built as an open stage, in which the characters are continuously „filmed” by the vigilant eye of Power. Behaviors become dissociated, identities – schizoid.

The priest is followed on the street, at services, but also in the area of his intimate life. In 1940, his little wife signed a pact with the Romanian Securitate, then with the Bolshevik KGB, and strictly followed the instructions to intimidate, slander, and annihilate her husband. The man's life with a woman he loves but does not trust is terrifying. Fear, insecurity, and distrust are the emotional poles around which the recollection gravitates.

If for other „enemies of the people”, only the extended family constituted an intimate, protective, and secure space, in Păduraru's case, the family is an extension of the terror of political power, through his wife Micuța. The couple's relationship is marked by suspicion and even hatred. „Although we had reconciled, our life was not normal. Micuța continued to look at me as if with the hostility from before, and I was afraid and did not trust her”¹⁰. Even after their relationship is consummated, many years later, revisiting his past, the narrator does not operate with certainties, reality is scrutinized with critical exigency and with the indulgence of preferring approximations and doubts over hasty stigmatizations.

„Whether he did this hoping he wouldn't find me alive or, on the contrary, to save my life, it's very difficult to say.”¹¹

10 Gherasim Păduraru, *Demascarea sau Taina porților zăvorâte. Memorialistică*. Chișinău, Editura Prut internațional, 2023, p.294.

11 Ibid., p. 265.

The evil caused by Micuta is understood and assumed as a consequence of the invincible force of the Security, which no one could oppose, especially a fragile woman like Micuta. The perfidious mechanisms of the Security are not fully elucidated even at a temporal distance from the events that occurred. The struggle, the agitation, the feverish search for answers build the emotional motive of the narrative.

„Now the question arises: who let this KGB agent into our house? And why did he open the door for him without my knowledge? Or why didn't he warn me that he was coming, why didn't he tell me when he came, especially since he was standing in the tent and listening to everything I was discussing with the little one and the others? Maybe that's why the little one kept me still for five months, namely from February 14 to July 17, 1962? Five months spent frozen in bed, with my back full of wounds, just so that the KGB could enjoy my words, which, to be honest, were not permeated with much love for them? And one more thing: who did this KGB agent come to, me or the little one? If he came to me, let my wife tell us, as a doctor, what could the KGB be looking for in a man so sick that, according to the doctors' orders, he was not even allowed to move his fingers? And if the KGB came to Micuta, it turns out that she had connections with them, and the fact that these connections were hidden from me meant that they were directed against me. In this case, I think the secret of the locked gates is clear.”¹². The narrative is full of reinterpretations, reinterpretations, nuances. The story is doubled by suspicion and existentially motivated speculative effort.

Gherasim Păduraru's „voice” is reporter-like, with a pressure of the factual, agglutinating a lot of information, often left without any psychological explanation. His son, Pavel, confesses that he tried not to interfere in the original and that „this book hides things that were very difficult for me to understand in places”¹³. However, in the pages of the book one can read the turmoil of a man who endured enormously and whose soul has definitively lost its peace and balance

In conclusion: the memoiristic discourse of the evoked writer represents a subjective and personal lens for focusing on individual and

12 Gherasim Păduraru, *Demascarea sau Taina porților zăvorâte. Memorialistică*. Chișinău, Editura Prut internațional, 2023, p.264.

13 Ibid., p.319.

collective history, on social life as a whole, circumscribed in a historical period of aggressive repression by the KGB and Soviet political, linguistic, psychological, geographical, etc. colonization of Bessarabia. One's own experience as a victim of aggressive otherness is a proof of resistance and human dignity that demands to be confessed, to serve as a guide for the younger generation through the nebulous worlds of the past and to sound an alarm on the relapses of an imperial discourse that still strongly marks our mentality¹⁴ (Terian, 2013, p. 128).

The effort to describe the personal experience of mental colonization by the state that aggresses the national community and the author's family in a special way is meritorious. Writing, even yielding to the pedagogical impulse, in a historical and moralizing sense, Gherasim Păduraru, but also other Bessarabian memoir authors, such as Nicolae Negru, Constantin Cheianu, Paula Erizanu, Larisa Turea, Alexei Vakulovski, etc., lend their support to the effort to decolonize historical memory through artistic expression. To what extent this can be successful in the third decade of the 21st century, in a community that faces difficult challenges, cannot yet be assessed. However, the imperative of memory and the response to violence and oppression, the desire to establish a continuity (familial, often) and a community of memory, is retained. In the absence of greater attention to the way in which this memory of the past will be constructed, its drifts can be problematic.

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